

1 High-Resolution Downscaling of Source Resolved PM_{2.5} Predictions Using 2 Machine Learning Models

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17 Abstract

18 Accurate predictions of source resolved atmospheric PM_{2.5} concentrations at high resolutions using
19 chemical transport models (CTMs) require expensive CTM simulations and development of high-
20 resolution emissions inventories. We use multiple machine learning (ML) approaches to
21 downscale coarse-resolution (36 x 36 km²) CTM predictions to 1 x 1 km² spatial resolution. ML
22 predictions include concentrations of the major chemical components of PM_{2.5} and the
23 contributions of its major emissions sources. Inputs for the ML models include 36 x 36 km² source
24 resolved CTM predicted concentrations of all PM_{2.5} components, meteorological data, and several
25 land-use (LU) variables. The output of our ML models is the 1 x 1 km² source-resolved
26 concentrations of all major PM_{2.5} components in southwestern Pennsylvania (5184 km² domain)
27 during February and July 2017. Models were trained and validated using 1 x 1 km² resolution
28 source- and species-resolved CTM predictions of PM_{2.5} from recent complementary studies. The
29 best overall performance was found using a random forest (RF) model, where species and source
30 resolved PM_{2.5} concentrations were reproduced with low normalized mean bias (|NMB| < 0.01).
31 The downscaling model captures the spatial distribution of PM_{2.5} both by component and source,
32 with some discrepancies when predicting the plumes of large point sources that have long-range
33 impacts. In a test of generalizability to unknown domains, the model differentiates well between
34 areas that are primarily urban, rural, or industrial but faces challenges with the reproduction of the

35 effects of large point sources of PM_{2.5} when entire quadrants are removed from the training data.
36 The results represent a proof of concept for downscaling low-resolution CTM predictions using
37 native high-resolution CTM predictions in training.

38

39 **1. Introduction**

40 Particulate matter with aerodynamic diameter less than 2.5 μm (PM_{2.5}) is a major
41 contributor to poor air quality throughout the United States. PM_{2.5} directly impacts visibility
42 (Seinfeld and Pandis, 2006) and is also a major public health concern. Exposure to PM_{2.5} has been
43 linked to both short- and long-term health effects including premature death due to increased risk
44 of cardiovascular disease, increased chance of heart attacks and strokes, and hindered lung
45 development and lung function in children and people with asthma (Dockery and Pope, 1994).
46 Knowledge of individual source contributions to total PM_{2.5} concentrations is vital for the
47 development of effective emissions control policies. For environmental justice applications, it is
48 also desirable to know these individual source contributions at high spatial resolution (Banzhaf et
49 al., 2019). Simulations of high spatial resolution (1 x 1 km grid cell size), source-resolved,
50 speciated atmospheric PM_{2.5} concentration using a state-of-the-art chemical transport model
51 (CTM) are computationally expensive even for relatively small simulation domains (Garcia et al.,
52 2022). This predicates an opportunity to apply machine learning algorithms, leveraging previous
53 simulation results, to estimate the output from a CTM predicting high spatial resolution and source-
54 resolved PM_{2.5} concentrations.

55 Machine learning techniques have been used in the forecasting of future PM_{2.5}
56 concentrations based on past observed values at monitoring stations. Support vector machines and
57 artificial neural networks have shown promising results for this prediction task (Voukantsis et al.,
58 2011; Bai et al., 2016; Prasad et al., 2016; Zhou et al., 2018; Karimian et al., 2019). However,
59 these applications are not designed for predicting the variability of PM_{2.5} concentrations in space
60 and are limited to predicting a value at the precise locations of individual monitoring sites. Shtein
61 et al. (2019) implemented a model driven by aerosol optical depth observations in lieu of CTM
62 data.

63 A handful of studies have sought to produce estimates of PM_{2.5} concentrations with high
64 temporal and spatial resolution (similar to that of CTM output) by incorporating CTM predictions
65 in the modelling framework. Xue et al. (2019) combined data from PM_{2.5} monitors, satellite aerosol

66 optical depth data, meteorological fields calculated using the Weather Research and Forecasting
67 (WRF) model, as well as predicted PM_{2.5} concentrations and composition as predicted by the
68 Community Multiscale Air Quality (CMAQ) model at a resolution of 36 x 36 km into an elastic-
69 net regression (Zou and Hastie, 2005) model to estimate PM_{2.5} concentrations in China from 2000-
70 2016. Estimates of PM_{2.5} were found to be in reasonable agreement with measurements at large
71 averaging timescales ($R^2 = 0.77$ for annual averaging). Vlasenko et al. (2021) implemented a 3-
72 layer artificial neural network to produce daily average concentrations of NO₂, SO₂, and ethane
73 over Europe at a resolution of 64 x 64 km. The predictive model in this study was trained on
74 CMAQ simulation results from 1979-2012 with WRF meteorology and constant emissions
75 calculated for 2012. The goal of that study was to develop a streamlined approach for testing future
76 emissions scenarios. The authors found that the neural network was able to predict concentrations
77 of the pollutants of interest with errors on the same order as those between two different CTMs.

78 Neural networks have also been used to downscale the spatial resolution of PM_{2.5}
79 predictions from a CTM. Di et al. (2016) used low-resolution (0.500° x 0.667°) GEOS-Chem PM_{2.5}
80 component concentrations, meteorological data, and land-use regression variables (population
81 density, road density, etc.) as inputs to a neural network that predicts PM_{2.5} at 1 x 1 km grid
82 resolution in the northeast United States. The meteorological and land-use terms were used to
83 downscale the GEOS-Chem output to a higher resolution, and this model was trained using
84 available speciated PM_{2.5} monitoring data as well as total PM_{2.5} measurements from 2001-2010.
85 The high-resolution predictions were correlated well with monitoring data ($R^2 = 0.85$ for all data
86 and $R^2 = 0.70-0.80$ for individual PM_{2.5} components on an annual basis). This model was
87 developed with the goal of assisting epidemiological analysis during the specific study period
88 (2001-2010) and area (northeast United States) for which the model was trained. Generalizability
89 to other time periods and locations was not considered. This study also lacked high temporal and
90 spatial resolution in training data. EPA measurements for PM_{2.5} composition are only available
91 every three or six days and are quite sparse in space. A similar approach based on GEOS-Chem
92 predictions was implemented by Yu et al. (2023).

93 Land use regression (LUR) models use various independent variables (e.g. population
94 density, restaurant count, road length, etc.) along with available pollutant measurements to capture
95 the spatial variation in pollutant concentrations away from monitoring sites (Hoek et al., 2008).
96 These models have difficulties in predicting the concentrations of major PM_{2.5} components such

97 as elemental carbon and organic aerosol and their sources (Wu et al., 2014) due to the high spatial
98 variability of these species. In general, the smaller number of speciated PM_{2.5} measurements is an
99 important limitation. The addition of satellite data can improve the ability of a LUR model to
100 predict species and sources (Rahman and Thurston, 2022), but performance is still moderate with
101 $R^2 = 0.67$ for elemental carbon and $R^2 = 0.73$ for traffic PM_{2.5} on an annual basis.

102 PM_{2.5} prediction downscaling studies in the past have been hampered by the lack of high-
103 resolution, source and species resolved PM_{2.5} concentration fields to support the training of
104 effective models. Instead, they have relied on monitoring data which are sparse in space and time.
105 These models may or may not be able to predict in spatial and temporal domains that are not
106 included in the training dataset. This is a difficult problem to address, however a generalizable
107 model for high resolution PM_{2.5} concentrations would be a useful tool for streamlined studies
108 without requiring the computational resources associated with CTMs and the development time
109 required for the appropriate high-resolution emission inventories.

110 In this study, we use land-use (LU) variables in combination with meteorological data and
111 low-resolution CTM predictions (36 x 36 km) to predict source-resolved, speciated PM_{2.5}
112 concentrations at high-resolution (1 x 1 km). The goal of this work is to develop a predictive
113 modeling framework that can provide high-resolution PM_{2.5} concentrations from low resolution
114 CTM simulations, eliminating the need to prepare high resolution emissions inventories and
115 perform computationally expensive high resolution CTM simulations. The proposed modeling
116 framework notably does not include any observations of PM_{2.5} concentrations. While the addition
117 of this type of data would likely improve the ability of the model to predict total PM_{2.5} in some
118 cases, this would extend beyond the scope of the current work which is to reproduce the 1 x 1 km²
119 CTM source- and species-resolved PM_{2.5} concentrations. Future work can include the addition of
120 measurements to the proposed approach. We explore the application of several machine learning
121 models for this task and evaluate the predicted speciated and source-resolved PM_{2.5} concentrations
122 by comparing them to the actual 1 x 1 km² resolution output of PMCAMx (Garcia, et al., 2022;
123 Dinkelacker et al., 2022). This work can be viewed as a first test of the feasibility of developing a
124 generalizable downscaling approach using high-resolution CTM predictions in selected areas.

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128 2. Model Description

129 The information flow of the downscaling model developed in this study is illustrated in
130 Figure 1. Inputs to the downscaling model include low-resolution ($36 \times 36 \text{ km}^2$) source and species
131 resolved $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ concentration predictions from PMCAMx, meteorological variables simulated
132 using WRF, and LU variables described below. The downscaling model is trained and validated
133 using high-resolution ($1 \times 1 \text{ km}^2$) source- and species-resolved $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ predictions from PMCAMx.
134 These source- and species- resolved high-resolution $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ predictions are the target variables for
135 the models described in the following sections.

136

137 2.1 Chemical Transport Model Predictions

138 Speciated and source-resolved predictions of $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ in southwestern Pennsylvania at $36 \times$
139 36 km and $1 \times 1 \text{ km}$ grid resolution for February and July 2017 are available based on the work of
140 Garcia Rivera et al. (2022). The high resolution $1 \times 1 \text{ km}^2$ domain in southwestern Pennsylvania
141 is used as the spatial domain for the following analyses. These concentration fields were produced
142 using the Particulate Matter Comprehensive Air Quality Model with Extensions (PMCAMx)
143 (Karydis et al., 2010; Murphy and Pandis, 2010; Tsimpidi et al., 2010), a state-of-the-science CTM
144 that uses the framework of the CAMx model (Environ, 2006). Simulated components of $\text{PM}_{2.5}$
145 include primary organic aerosol (POA), secondary organic aerosol (SOA), elemental carbon (EC),
146 crustal mass (CRST), nitrate, ammonium, and sulfate. Detailed descriptions of PMCAMx can be
147 found in Fountoukis et al. (2011) and Zakoura and Pandis (2019). Seven emissions source
148 categories are considered: (1) biomass burning, (2) cooking, (3) on-road vehicles, (4) power
149 generation, (5) industrial activities, (6) miscellaneous area sources (solvent utilization,
150 storage/transport of petroleum products, dry cleaning, waste disposal/incineration), and (7) "other"
151 emissions sources (e.g. agricultural dust, river barges, off-road vehicles and equipment, rail
152 activity, and oil-gas activities). Additionally, the contribution to $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ concentrations from sources
153 located outside of the simulation domain is quantified and referred to as long-range transport
154 (LRT) $\text{PM}_{2.5}$. The average contribution to total $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ concentrations in February and July 2017 by
155 source are provided in Figure S1. Daily average PMCAMx predictions of $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ concentration
156 from 56 species/source combinations (i.e., six chemical components as well as total $\text{PM}_{2.5}$; seven
157 source categories as well as LRT) are available for the 5184 km^2 simulation domain at 36×36
158 km^2 and $1 \times 1 \text{ km}^2$ grid resolution. The simulation area is comprised of a large portion of

159 southwestern Pennsylvania (including the urban area of Pittsburgh), as well as parts of eastern
160 Ohio and northern West Virginia. The low-resolution PM_{2.5} predictions are used as input for the
161 downscaling model. while the high-resolution predictions are used to train and validate the
162 downscaling model.

163 The source- and species-resolved CTM predictions of total PM_{2.5} mass and all major PM_{2.5}
164 components at both grid resolutions have been evaluated using all available regulatory data in the
165 southwestern Pennsylvania as well as aerosol mass spectrometer (AMS) data available from the
166 Carnegie Mellon University Supersite. Importantly, the CTM reproduced urban-rural PM_{2.5}
167 gradients at 1 x 1 km² resolution, with performance against stationary monitors improving with
168 increasing grid resolution. Total PM_{2.5} mass concentrations were predicted well in the winter with
169 low fractional error (0.3) and fractional bias (+0.05). In the summer period, total PM_{2.5} was
170 underpredicted (fractional bias = -0.39) due to corresponding underpredictions of organic aerosol
171 (OA). Improvement of biogenic secondary OA formation mechanisms in PMCAMx is in active
172 development to address this issue. Further detailed evaluation of this data can be found in
173 Dinkelacker et al. (2022). The subsequently developed machine learning models inherit the
174 performance of the CTM data used in training, but the methodology described in this work is
175 general and can be applied to any other CTM or take advantage of future improvements to
176 PMCAMx.

177

178 *2.2 Meteorology*

179 Meteorological fields were first calculated using the Weather Research and Forecasting
180 model (WRF-v3.6.1) with horizontal resolution of 12 x 12 km. Initial and boundary conditions
181 were obtained from the ERA-Interim global climate re-analysis database. Required WRF input
182 data including terrain, land-use, and soil type were retrieved from the United States Geological
183 Survey database. WRF output was then interpolated to 1 x 1 km grid resolution. Temperature,
184 wind velocity, and wind direction from these meteorological simulations are used at inputs for the
185 downscaling models tested in this study. An evaluation of the performance of these spatially
186 interpolated meteorological variables was performed to accompany the original analysis of CTM
187 results. A summary of the evaluation of the high-resolution meteorological variables can be found
188 in Dinkelacker et al. (2022). In general, the evaluation showed that the errors in magnitude and

189 phasing of the diurnal cycles of the interpolated variables are appropriately small for use in CTM
190 simulations.

191

192 *2.3 Land Use Variables*

193 The LU variables used in this study are from a database compiled by Kim et al. (2020). For
194 each variable, values are available for every census block across the contiguous United States at a
195 range of buffer sizes (100 m to 15 km), referring to the radius of aggregation of that variable with
196 respect to the census block centroid. In total, we selected 24 variables for use in this study (as
197 inputs to the downscaling models): road length and type, restaurant count, population, elevation,
198 impervious land area, and 14 characterizations of land use (e.g. residential land, industrial land,
199 urban green space, forested land, etc.). To map the data to the 1 x 1 km² resolution simulation grid,
200 data from the nearest census block to each computational cell in the downscaling model was used
201 (smallest centroid-to-centroid distance). For each variable, we selected only one radius: when a
202 1000 m radius was available in the dataset, we used that value; a 3000 m radius was used for four
203 variables (length of A2 road, industrial area, mixed-urban area, and residential area) when 1000 m
204 data was not available.

205

206 *2.4 Algorithms Used for Resolution Downscaling*

207 Four algorithms were tested in this study to determine their suitability as estimators for
208 high-resolution, source- and species-resolved PM_{2.5} predictions. (1) A multiple linear regression
209 (MLR) scheme was tested as a zeroth level approach. With the MLR model, an individual linear
210 model is fit to describe the relationship between one of the output variables and all of the input
211 variables. This type of approach cannot capture nonlinear relationships between inputs and
212 outputs. (2) A 3-hidden layer artificial neural network (NN) similar to the architecture used in
213 previous studies (Di et al., 2016; Vlasenko et al., 2021), where the model includes multiple layers
214 of nodes. The output of each node is computed by some non-linear function of its inputs. The
215 weights that determine these functions are updated during training, resulting in a more accurate
216 model. (3) A simple decision tree (DT) framework (Breiman et al., 1984) was tested. In this
217 framework, the dataset gets divided into smaller and smaller subsets based on subsequent
218 conditional statements. These conditional statements are made by determining what split can be
219 made on the data that results in the greatest decrease in standard deviation of the data after splitting.

220 (4) A random forest (RF) model (Breiman et al., 2001) was tested. This type of model is trained to
221 return the average prediction of a large number of decision trees that have been trained on random
222 parts of the training dataset. Use of these machine learning algorithms is motivated by the need for
223 capturing inherent nonlinearities associated with air quality modeling. Scikit-Learn (Pedregosa et
224 al., 2011) implementations for linear regression, decision tree, and random forest models were
225 used. The Keras TensorFlow (Abadi et al., 2015) package was used to formulate the neural network
226 model.

227 In all cases, a scaling function was applied to all variables (PM_{2.5} concentrations,
228 meteorological variables, LUR variables) of the downscaling model in order to set the range of
229 these variables to [-1, 1]. This is done to prevent training bias towards a variable with a larger
230 range of values. For example, the value of population ranges from 0 to 18000 people, while the
231 value of PM_{2.5} POA at coarse resolution (36 x 36 km²) ranges from 0 to 4 µg m⁻³ even though both
232 of these inputs are provided to the same model. These input variables may be of equal importance
233 for making predictions, but the magnitudes of their values differ tremendously. The variable with
234 the higher magnitude will tend to have a disproportionate impact on model predictions, so scaling
235 is important before training a predictive model. The variables were scaled according to:

$$236 \quad X_{scaled} = \frac{2(X - X_{min})}{X_{max} - X_{min}} - 1 \quad (1)$$

238 where X_{scaled} is the scaled vector of all values for a single variable, X is the vector pre-scaling, X_{min}
239 is the minimum value in the vector, and X_{max} is the maximum value in the vector. After predictions
240 are made, an inverse function is applied to calculate the predicted concentrations to their original
241 ranges.
242

243 For model training, the high-resolution cells were randomly divided into ten 10% to 90%
244 splits. Models were trained on the 90% splits and tested on the remaining 10% of cells. Training
245 and testing were repeated on each set (ten total) and performance metrics were averaged for the
246 formal analysis. Cells were randomly split at first, however nonrandom splits were used as a tool
247 for model evaluation. Data from both February and July 2017 periods are included in the training
248 dataset, with the only obvious indicator variable of which month a data point is from being
249 temperature. The same model is used for both February and July to strive towards temporal

250 generalizability. To visually present the ability of the model to reproduce the spatial distribution
 251 of source-resolved PM_{2.5} and its components, five unique and random 20% to 80% splits were
 252 used so that the test predictions cover the entire spatial domain. This enables map generation while
 253 avoiding making predictions on grid cells that exist in any of the training sets.

254

255 *2.5 Predictive Performance Metrics*

256 All predictions made on testing data inputs are evaluated by comparing predictions of
 257 species- and source-resolved PM_{2.5} with the daily high-resolution PMCAMx simulation results.
 258 Evaluation metrics considered are the normalized root mean squared error (NRMSE), normalized
 259 mean error (NME), and normalized mean bias (NMB):

$$260 \quad NRMSE = \sqrt{\frac{\sum_{k=1}^N (P_k - O_k)^2}{N}} / O_{mean} \quad (2)$$

261

$$262 \quad NMB = \sum_{k=1}^N (P_k - O_k) / \sum_{k=1}^N O_k \quad (3)$$

263

$$264 \quad NME = \sum_{k=1}^N |P_k - O_k| / \sum_{k=1}^N O_k \quad (4)$$

265

266 where P_k is the k^{th} predicted daily value of the output PM_{2.5} concentration (aggregated by species
 267 or source), O_k is the k^{th} "true" daily value of the PM_{2.5} concentration, N is the total number of data
 268 points, and O_{mean} is the mean value of the "true" PM_{2.5} concentration. In the context of this
 269 methodology, the "true" value refers to the PM_{2.5} concentration that was calculated by the CTM at
 270 1 x 1 km² resolution. The evaluation metrics are calculated after performing the necessary inverse
 271 variable scaling. We evaluate here the ability of each algorithm to downscale predictions of each
 272 PM_{2.5} component as well as total PM_{2.5} from each source category.

273

274 **3. Results and Discussion**

275 *3.1 Algorithm Screening*

276 Figure 2 illustrates the NRMSE of test set predictions of PM_{2.5} components and total PM_{2.5}
 277 mass. As expected, the MLR model has overall the weakest performance in terms of NRMSE. The
 278 linear model does exhibit better performance with NRMSE < 0.1 for SOA predictions (NRMSE <

279 0.1) because this component has much less variation in space compared to other PM_{2.5} components.
280 The NN and DT algorithms offer significant improvements compared to the linear model. NN and
281 DT produce similar results in terms of NRMSE by species, with the neural network predicting
282 some species (POA, EC, CRST) with slightly lower error and the decision tree performing better
283 with the rest (SOA, ammonium, nitrate, sulfate). The RF algorithm predicts all species with the
284 lowest error, although in most cases the difference is small compared to NN and DT. For total
285 PM_{2.5} predictions, the NRMSE achieved with the random forest algorithm is around 0.01 less than
286 that of the neural network and decision tree algorithms.

287 The performance (NRMSE) of the various algorithms for source-resolved PM_{2.5}
288 predictions is summarized in Figure 3. NME and NMB values are available in Table S2 in the
289 supplementary material. The linear model again has the worst performance, while the NN and RF
290 algorithms have the best. The NRMSE of predictions made using RF is lower than NN for power
291 generation (0.2 lower), but higher for cooking (0.2 higher) and industrial sources (0.13 higher).
292 The rest of the predictions are similar or show slightly better performance using the RF. Scatter
293 plots depicting the performance of each algorithm with regards to total PM_{2.5} concentration are
294 shown in Figure 4. Total PM_{2.5} is predicted very well by the NN, DT, and RF models (NME <
295 0.05; |NMB| < 0.01). For cooking PM_{2.5}, the NN and RF algorithms predictions have little absolute
296 normalized bias (less than 0.012). With industrial PM_{2.5} we see enormous improvements from the
297 linear model, especially at high concentrations. Here, the lowest bias (|NMB| = 0.002-0.003) is
298 achieved using any of the NN, DT, or RF algorithms.

299 Our analysis up to this point supports the use of the random forest algorithm due to
300 consistently low error and bias in predictions, regardless of PM_{2.5} species or source category.
301 Additional scatter plots for all other PM_{2.5} species and source categories are included in the
302 supplementary material (Figures S2-S12). In the remaining sections we will focus on the results
303 of the RF algorithm.

304

305 *3.2 Spatial Distribution of Monthly Averaged Predictions*

306 In general, the downscaling model reproduces the spatial distribution of PM_{2.5} in
307 southwestern Pennsylvania well for both February and July 2017. The downscaling model captures
308 both the peak PM_{2.5} concentrations in downtown Pittsburgh and those near the industrial facilities
309 in the northwestern part of the domain (Figure 5). The urban to rural transition outside of the city

310 of Pittsburgh is also captured. Some inconsistencies on the order of $0.1 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ are seen with $\text{PM}_{2.5}$
311 species with considerable emissions from large point sources. An example of this is $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ sulfate
312 which has large emissions from power generation in the upper left and lower left corners of the
313 domain (Figure 6).

314 The ability of the downscaling model to differentiate between two distinct time periods is
315 shown in the monthly average maps for biomass burning $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ (Figure 7). This source shows the
316 greatest variability between months. In February the domain-average, minimum, and maximum
317 concentration of biomass burning $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ as predicted by PMCAMx are $0.8 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$, $0.02 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$,
318 and $3.31 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ respectively. In July, the corresponding values are $0.007 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$, $0.0005 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$,
319 and $0.036 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$. In February, the downscaling model reproduces both the large peak values as
320 well as the large sections of the domain where the concentration is low. In July, it is encouraging
321 that the downscaling model does not predict any large concentrations of biomass burning $\text{PM}_{2.5}$
322 anywhere throughout the simulation domain. With power generation $\text{PM}_{2.5}$, small inconsistencies
323 in predictions follow those seen with $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ sulfate. This occurs because the emissions from sources
324 like power generation originate from just a few large localized sources, but travel large distances
325 across the entire domain. The LUR variables provide the downscaling model with high-resolution
326 information about emissions sources (restaurants, population, industrial land-use area, etc.) within
327 a radius of 1 km. This means that far away from a large point source, the machine learning
328 algorithm has no direct knowledge of an emissions source like a power plant that could be
329 impacting $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ concentrations at the location of interest far beyond the 1 km radius. Despite this
330 lack of information, the RF model reproduces well the major plumes of $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ from power
331 generation sources, however with the small inconsistencies present throughout the domain. This
332 is due to the random nature of the training and testing data splits. Increasing the radius of LUR
333 variables such as industrial land use may improve performance for these sources. Maps of monthly
334 average $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ concentrations for all other major species and sources are included in the
335 supplementary material (Figures S13 - S23).

336

337 *3.3 Additional model testing for “new” areas*

338 As a preliminary test of the generalizability of this downscaling approach, we trained the
339 model by holding out entire quadrants of the domain as testing data, rather than a randomly
340 selected subset of 25% of the $1 \times 1 \text{ km}^2$ cells. The training of the model did not include any

341 information for this held-out area. The quadrant-based approach was chosen to challenge the
342 model in terms of predicting $PM_{2.5}$ concentrations in unknown, relatively large, contiguous
343 domains while also aligning with the grid cells in the low-resolution CTM predictions. This
344 procedure was followed for each quadrant, and the results of this test are shown in Figures 9
345 (February) and 10 (July). In the northwest and southwest quadrants, we see the expected effects
346 from long range sources of $PM_{2.5}$. The downscaling model has difficulties in reproducing large
347 emissions plumes due to the relatively small radius associated with the land-use information (1-3
348 km) compared to the range of the visible plumes (up to 40 km). In the northeast quadrant, the
349 downscaling model tends to spread the effects of the downtown Pittsburgh area to a wider area.
350 The downtown area is a unique feature in this domain, so it is not surprising that the downscaling
351 model has difficulty reproducing the spatial distribution of $PM_{2.5}$ in this area without an additional
352 urban center in the training data. The downscaling model reproduces the spatial distribution of
353 $PM_{2.5}$ in the southeast quadrant, which has both significant population and industrial activity. With
354 its obvious challenges to reproduce certain large emissions features (large emissions stacks,
355 discrete urban centers, etc.), the model clearly differentiates between areas that are primarily urban,
356 rural, or industrial when faced with the challenge of predicting over contiguous subdomains that
357 contain valuable information for training a machine learning model. This result is encouraging
358 ahead of the application of this downscaling model to other locations in the United States. The
359 improvement of the treatment of the effects of large point emission sources will be a topic of future
360 study.

361

362 **4. Conclusions**

363 Four algorithms were tested to downscale the resolution of CTM (PMCAMx) predictions
364 of source-resolved speciated $PM_{2.5}$ concentration from a coarse resolution of $36 \times 36 \text{ km}^2$ grid cell
365 size to $1 \times 1 \text{ km}^2$ in southwestern Pennsylvania during the months of February and July 2017.
366 Additional inputs to the downscaling model include high-resolution meteorological variables and
367 LU variables to capture high-resolution spatial variability in emissions sources. The RF approach
368 reproduces the high-resolution CTM output for all $PM_{2.5}$ species except crustal $PM_{2.5}$ with low
369 NRMSE (< 0.11), with the most obvious inconsistencies present with species associated with large
370 point sources such as $PM_{2.5}$ sulfate, a major component of power generation emissions. The RF
371 model does especially well at predicting total $PM_{2.5}$ (NRMSE < 0.1 , NMB < 0.001). The RF model

372 also does well at capturing the major emissions features in the source-resolved predictions. In
373 particular, the ability of the model to accurately reproduce $PM_{2.5}$ from sources that are significantly
374 different in contribution between the two months is encouraging. The RF algorithm was chosen to
375 further test the ability of a predictive model to reproduce high-resolution predictions of speciated
376 and source-resolved $PM_{2.5}$ as predicted by PMCAMx. Minor inconsistencies in model predictions
377 are only seen for $PM_{2.5}$ from sources that have long-range effects far from the point of emission.
378 With these sources (power generation, industrial), the 1-3 km radius for land-use information may
379 not be far enough for the model to learn well the long-range effects. To improve performance with
380 these sources, larger radii on the order of the range of these sources (~10 km) will be tested in
381 future work. While the performance of the downscaling model is encouraging, it is important that
382 the model be viable in other locales provided sufficient input information. Preliminary tests of
383 model generalizability were explored within the southwestern Pennsylvania domain by training
384 downscaling models using entire domain quadrants as testing data. The downscaling model
385 struggles to reproduce large emissions plumes in the northwest and southwest quadrants, again
386 suggesting the need for longer range land-use information for power generation and industrial
387 sources. The downscaling model also tends to spread out the urban $PM_{2.5}$ in the northeast quadrant.
388 The ability of the downscaling model to differentiate between largely urban, rural, and industrial
389 areas is encouraging, understanding that important features had to be removed from training
390 datasets to carry out these tests. Future work will also involve compiling the requisite input data
391 for application of this model to other cities in the United States, where the predictions will be
392 evaluated against available $PM_{2.5}$ measurements.

393
394 *Author contributions.* BTD performed the PMCAMx simulations, prepared all data for
395 downscaling models, implemented the predictive models in Python, analyzed the results, and wrote
396 the manuscript. PGR prepared anthropogenic emissions and other inputs for the PMCAMx
397 simulations and assisted in preparation of PMCAMx output. SNP, PJA, and JDM designed and
398 coordinated the study and helped in the writing of the paper. All authors reviewed and commented
399 on the manuscript.

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401 *Competing Interests.* The authors declare that they have no conflict of interest.

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512 **Figure 1.** Information flow for resolution downscaling of chemical transport model PM_{2.5}

513 concentration predictions. All predictors and target variables are of daily temporal resolution,

514 with the exception of land-use information which is static.

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Figure 2. Normalized root mean squared error (NRMSE) of testing set PM_{2.5} predictions by species for various algorithms when compared to daily high-resolution PMCAMx predictions.

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Figure 3. Normalized root mean squared error (NRMSE) of testing set PM_{2.5} predictions by source category for various algorithms when compared to daily high-resolution PMCAMx predictions.

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Figure 4. Prediction performance of (a) linear regression, (b) neural network, (c) decision tree, and (d) random forest algorithms on test set total $PM_{2.5}$ concentrations compared to the "true" daily concentrations predicted by PMCAMx. $n = 26950$

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Figure 5. Maps of monthly average ground level total $PM_{2.5}$ for February and July 2017 as predicted by PMCAMx and the random forest model.

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Figure 6. Maps of monthly average ground level $PM_{2.5}$ sulfate for February and July 2017 as predicted by PMCAMx and the random forest model.

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Figure 7. Maps of monthly average ground level total PM_{2.5} from biomass burning sources for February and July 2017 as predicted by PMCAMx and the random forest model.

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Figure 8. Maps of monthly average ground level total $PM_{2.5}$ from power generation sources for February and July 2017 as predicted by PMCAMx and the random forest model.

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 555 **Figure 9.** Maps of monthly average ground level total $PM_{2.5}$ in southwestern Pennsylvania for
 556 February 2017 as predicted by (a) PMCAMx high-res, (b) RF model with entire quadrant testing
 557 sets, and (c) PMCAMx low-res.
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 561 **Figure 10.** Maps of monthly average ground level total $PM_{2.5}$ in southwestern Pennsylvania for
 562 July 2017 as predicted by (a) PMCAMx high-res, (b) RF model with entire quadrant testing sets,
 563 and (c) PMCAMx low-res.
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